

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D8.5 Guidance and recommendations to enhance the citizen response

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Deliverable

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Authors	Annika Herbertz, SINUS James Edwards, SINUS Isabella Tautscher, SINUS
Contributors	All partners
Reviewers	Elena Ambrosetti, SAPIENZA

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Executive Summary

The COVINFORM project examined how vulnerability is defined and addressed in response to the COVID-19 outbreak. The project drew upon complex adaptive system and intersectional approaches to offer a multilevel and interdisciplinary critique of COVID-19 responses on the levels of government, public health, community, information & communications, as well as resident perspective, and how these responses may exacerbate vulnerability and marginalisation. The current deliverable D8.5 give a summary of the outputs produced in work package 6, “Citizen and community responses and impact assessment”, in the form of deliverables, white papers, a bi-monthly report, blog posts, a podcast, videos, and other public outputs shared on the project website. It draws on the work conducted in work package 6, which analysed COVID-19’s impact and response from a community and citizen perspective, with a specific focus on vulnerability.

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Introduction

The COVINFORM project examined how vulnerability is defined and addressed in response to the COVID-19 outbreak. The project drew upon complex adaptive system and intersectional approaches to offer a multilevel and interdisciplinary critique of COVID-19 responses on the levels of government, public health, community, information & communications, as well as resident perspective, and how these responses may exacerbate vulnerability and marginalisation.

Deliverable D8.6 presents a summary of the WP6 outputs, as well as transversal project outputs that are relevant to the WP6 topic of community and citizen responses and impacts, e.g.:

- Impacts and responses in selected sub-national research sites ('geographical communities')
- Impacts on and responses by specific population groups ('non-geographical communities')
- Civil society organisation responses and participatory practices, i.e., responses that actively involved ordinary residents in significant ways ('citizen responses')

Note that some of these outputs are relevant for several of the work packages, and are hence presented multiple times across D8.3 to 8.6. The below table summarises all project outputs relevant to the topics of community and citizen responses.

Table 1. Overview of outputs on community and citizen responses and impacts written in the context of WP6

Number	Month	Title	Topics covered	Lead partner or authors
DELIVERABLES				
D6.1	August 2021	Baseline report: Community and citizen responses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desk research on impacts in the target municipalities 	Elena Ambrosetti & Allesandra De Rose (SAPIENZA)
D6.2	December 2021	Research design: Community and citizen responses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research design: empirical research with CSO representatives and residents in the target municipalities 	James Edwards (SINUS)
D6.3	November 2020	Community and citizen responses and impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Findings of empirical research with CSO representatives in the target municipalities 	KEMEA, SINUS, AUTRC, TRI, SYNYO, UANTWERPEN, UGOT & SU
D6.4	June 2022	Synthesis and lessons learnt on community and citizen responses and impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of research findings within the COVINFORM vulnerability assessment model and social-ecological systems framework 	James Edwards (SINUS) & Viktoria Adler (SYNYO)
D6.5	October 2022	Baseline report: Community and citizen responses - update M24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated desk research on participatory practices in the target municipalities 	Marina Zannella & Elena Ambrosetti (SAPIENZA) & James Edwards (SINUS)
D6.6	February 2023	Research design: Community and citizen responses - update M28	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated research design, including formalised research questions 	James Edwards (SINUS)
D6.7	August 2023	Analysis: Community and citizen responses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated findings of empirical research with CSO 	Ioannis Bagkatzounis, Anna Tsekoura &

		and impact – update M34	representatives in the target municipalities	Ioannis Konstantopoulos (KEMEA)
D6.8	October 2023	Synthesis and lessons learnt on community and citizen responses and impacts – Update M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Updated analysis of research findings with regard to formalised research questions, as well as the COVINFORM vulnerability assessment model and social-ecological systems framework 	James Edwards & Helen Rademacher (SINUS)
WHITE PAPERS				
1	October 2023	Participatory practices during COVID-19: Research findings and policy recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Insight into participatory practises, alongside with policy recommendations 	Isabella Tautscher, James Edwards, Helen Rademacher & Annika Herberz (SINUS)
2	October 2023	A social-ecological systems view on COVID-19: Research findings and policy recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analysis of the COVID-19 pandemic using the Social-ecological-systems framework, alongside with policy recommendations 	James Edwards (SINUS)
BI-MONTHLY REPORTS				
1	September 2021	Using an intersectional lens to understand the unequal impact of the COVID-19 pandemic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examination of COVID-19 impact and responses across partner countries, considering the role of intersectionality's role in understanding and addressing pre-existing structural inequalities 	Jil Molenaar (UANTWERPEN)
2	September 2022	Resilience in the Systems we live in: 10 European case studies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview of the 10 COVINFORM case studies aiming to identify vulnerability and protective factors of both vulnerable populations and systems 	Patrick Love & Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto (FS)
3	September 2021	A civil society organisation perspective on vulnerability: Lessons learned during COVID-19	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lessons learnt by CSOs about vulnerability during the COVID-19 pandemic based on qualitative interviews conducted with representatives & desk research 	James Edwards (SINUS)
4	January 2023	'Closer to death': thinking about dying in pandemic times	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analysis of changing relationships people have had with dead during the COVID-19 pandemic based on a study survey 	Diana Beljaars & Sergei Shubin (SU)
5	September 2020	Migrant women during the pandemic: multiple and intertwined vulnerabilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analysis of qualitative interviews in partner countries with migrant women, focusing on how they obtained information and formal/informal support during the pandemic 	Elena Ambrosetti (SAPIENZA), Irene Sánchez-Vitores (URJC)
BLOG POSTS				

1	October 2023	Emergency medical service responders reflect on the pandemic: Interventions in Israel and Spain – Part I	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiences and reflections of emergency medical service (EMS) responders in Israel and Spain amid the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic 	James Edwards (SINUS)
2	October 2023	Emergency medical service responders reflect on the pandemic: Interventions in Israel and Spain – Part II	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuation of previous blog post on experiences of EMS responders in Israel and Spain 	James Edwards (SINUS)
3	September 2023	Understanding the Systems we Live in: Deconstructing the Systems we Live by	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concept of syndemics, overlap of epidemics with social and cultural problems 	Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto (FS)
4	June 2023	How COVID-19 has exposed housing inequalities: insights from Antwerp	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expansion of housing inequalities in Antwerp due to the COVID-19 pandemic based on interviews with migrants 	Hanna Robinson (UANTWERPEN)
5	December, 2022	Where did the UK go wrong in preparing for the COVID-19 pandemic, and how have preparedness failings tainted public trust among the UK population?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UK's response to COVID-19 pandemic with a focus on key failings and their effect on the public trust in the governments pandemic handling 	Zainab Mehdi (TRI)
6	July 2022	Compulsory vaccinations and skipping contact restrictions – differing narratives of freedom in the German middle class	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Middle-class perspectives on COVID-19 vaccinations and compulsory vaccination, link to the SINUS-milieus 	James Edwards & Tim Gensheimer (SINUS)
7	April 2022	“Un-masking the Mask-Issue”: Examining People’s Sense-Making Processes and Risk-Cultural Norms regarding Facemasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cultural norms and values influencing people’s perceptions of facemasks in Sweden during the COVID-19 pandemic 	Tim Arasimowicz (UGOT)
8	December 2021	Antisemitic narratives find ground in COVID-19 anti-vax conspiracy theories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intersection of antisemitic narratives and COVID-19 anti-vax conspiracy theories, and the role of social media in spreading such ideologies 	Marianna Karakoulaki (MDI)
9	November 2021	Pandemic mitigation for everyone: Ethnic differences in Wales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ethnic differences in perceptions and responses to the COVID-19 pandemic and mitigation measures in Wales 	Diana Beljaars, Sergei Shubin & Louise Condon (SU)
10	August 2021	Why gender matters in the COVID-19 response	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gendered impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic like employment exposure, economic disparities and domestic violence 	Su Anson (TRI), Viktoria Adler (SYNYO), Diotima Bertel (SYNYO) & Maureen Fordham
PODCAST				
1	February 2023	Community voices – Bringing it all together	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stories from CSO’s shedding light on the experiences of 	Eliza Jordan (TRI), James Edwards (SINUS),

			vulnerable groups during the COVID-19 pandemic	Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto (FS)
VIDEOS				
2	October 2023	Elements of community – Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to the “Elements of community” and how CSO’s leveraged these to support their communities during the COVID-19 pandemic 	James Edwards (SINUS)
3	October 2023	Elements of community – Shared locations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on the Element of community “Shared location” 	Ilka Sobotka (external stakeholder)
4	October 2023	Elements of community -- Diversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on the Element of community “Diversity” 	Ilka Sobotka (external stakeholder)
5	October 2023	Elements of community – Joint action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on the Element of community “Joint action” 	Markus Priller (AUTRC)
6	October 2023	Elements of community – Shared characteristics and behaviours	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on the Element of community “Shared characteristics and behaviours” 	Dr. Suad Mohamed (AUTRC)
7	October 2023	Elements of community – Social Ties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on the Element of community “Social Ties” 	Chaim Rafalowski (MDA)
SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS				
1	December 2022	Migrants as ‘vulnerable groups’ in the COVID-19 pandemic: A critical discourse analysis of a taken-for-granted label in academic literature	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical examination of the academic usage of ‘vulnerable’ concerning migrants during the COVID-19 pandemic, revealing widespread generalization, contradictions in policy implications, and marginalization of migrants’ perspectives, suggesting a shift from a fixed descriptor to the dynamic concept of ‘vulnerabilisation’ influenced by social order and power relations 	Jil Molenaar, Lore Van Praag (UAMSTERDAM)
2	2022	Reproductions of vulnerability: The inequitable realities of the Welsh policy and pandemic response procedures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How COVID-19 and the governmental responses to the pandemic in Wales affect the experiences of groups that faced relatively high levels of suffering, illness, and death 	Diana Beljaars, Sergei Shubin, Louise Condon (SU)
3	2023	Constructing viral subjectivities during the pandemic: women’s embodiment in Wales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lived pandemic subjectivities of minority ethnic women with a low socio-economic status in South Wales 	Diana Beljaars, Sergei Shubin (SU)
4	In review	A Beacon of Hope: A Qualitative Study on Migrants’ Mental Health Needs and Community-Based Organizations’ Responses During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Antwerp, Belgium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment of how community organisations have responded to mental health needs during the pandemic 	Hannah Robinson, Jil Molenaar, Lore van Praag (UANTWERPEN)

5	In review	Feeling Stuck: The Micro-Politics of Migrant Dwelling Practices During COVID-19 in Antwerp	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Exploration how migrant micro-politics took place within a context of spatial inequalities during the pandemic	Hannah Robinson, Jil Molenaar, Lore van Praag (UANTWERPEN)
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2 Deliverables

D6.1 Baseline report: Community and citizen responses

Lead beneficiary: SAPIENZA

This report outlines the local community structures, stakeholder networks, and responses across COVINFORM target countries, conducting desk research on community-level response plans and emergent citizen responses in sub-national units of each partner country. The report introduces its aims, provides a rationale for considering local communities during the pandemic, and explains the research design methodology. It presents the work done in each partner country, offering baseline reports with top-level descriptive analyses. The findings highlight that the impact of the pandemic was more severe in large cities, and good practices emerged from public-private partnerships, involving volunteers, NGOs, religious communities, and local administrations to meet the needs of vulnerable populations. The report emphasizes that it will be updated with the analysis of community and citizen responses in the target sub-national units in M24.

D6.2 Research design: Community and citizen responses

Lead beneficiary: SINUS

In Work Package 6 of the COVINFORM project, the focus is on understanding the community-level impacts of COVID-19 and the corresponding multi-level policy responses. This document, part of Task 6.2, outlines the planned empirical research, beginning with an overview of project and WP6 objectives. It summarizes the findings of desk research (T6.1) on COVID-19 impacts and responses in sub-national research sites, identifying common factors such as local socio-ecological parameters, diverse actors' participation, and transnational relevance of successful practices. Drawing on theoretical work from WP3, 4, and 5, the deliverable establishes a theoretical framework for researching COVID-19 impacts and policy responses within the concept of "community." It defines "community," synthesizes it with socio-ecological systems, and formulates research questions. Target populations include civil society organization representatives and residents in research sites, studied using qualitative methods like problem-centred interviews. The document concludes with details on recruitment, data analysis, and annexes presenting research procedures and data collection instruments.

D6.3 Analysis: Community and citizen responses and impacts

Lead beneficiary: KEMEA

This deliverable offers an initial descriptive analysis of interviews with 38 representatives from civil society organizations and grassroots initiatives involved in COVID-19 responses across nine European municipalities. Focusing on municipal/sub-municipal levels, the report explores how local conditions and actors influenced the pandemic's impacts and responses. Key themes include local baseline conditions, COVID-19 impact timelines, and multi-stakeholder responses. The findings reveal that the neighborhoods were characterized as highly diverse and socioeconomically disadvantaged, with vulnerability understood in an intersectional way. Civil society organizations played a crucial role in addressing the needs of vulnerable groups, often collaborating with various stakeholders. The onset of the pandemic significantly impacted the quality of life for vulnerable individuals, exacerbating

existing challenges. Local multi-stakeholder responses, including the role of civil society, were highlighted, with a mixed assessment of government actions. The report also notes positive aspects like increased volunteerism and recognition of CSOs. These findings inform ongoing research within the COVINFORM project, with resident interviews contributing to future iterations of the deliverable.

D6.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on community and citizen responses and impacts

Lead beneficiary: SINUS

This deliverable synthesizes the findings from Work Package 6, focusing on citizen and community responses to COVID-19. It aligns these findings with the COVINFORM vulnerability assessment model and the social-ecological systems framework. The report maps Civil Society Organization (CSO) interview findings across dimensions such as direct threats, vulnerabilities, consequences, and resilience. Lessons drawn include the multidimensional nature of vulnerability, the cascading effects of threats meeting vulnerabilities, the interconnectedness of vulnerabilities and resources, and the role of CSOs as "bridging organizations" in multilevel governance. The report concludes by linking multidimensional vulnerability to intersectionality, which will be further explored in forthcoming interviews with a specific vulnerable group: women with a low socio-economic status.

D6.5 Baseline report: Community and citizen responses – Update M24

Lead beneficiary: SAPIENZA

This deliverable focuses on Question 4 by identifying, describing, and analyzing 150 participatory practices across diverse local contexts in target countries and municipalities. The analysis reveals that these practices had both short-term and long-term aims, addressing areas beyond core social welfare systems and targeting chronic structural inequalities. They involved various actor configurations, including self-organized groups of residents, civil society organizations (CSOs), and governmental organizations (GOs). These practices ranged from single-service initiatives to comprehensive programs spanning multiple domains. While often utilizing online channels, they frequently involved field activities, exemplified by online platforms facilitating face-to-face support. The findings suggest that participatory practices achieved positive outcomes by addressing critical needs during systemic stress, supplementing or providing alternatives to governmental services, reducing barriers, and mitigating unintended consequences of policies like lockdowns. The deliverable suggests that future research should involve national authorities and the actors to systematically analyze practices and outcomes. Additionally, participatory practices contribute to social resilience by enhancing social capital, advancing social learning, and preserving social memory, offering valuable lessons for adaptive crisis management like the COVID-19 pandemic.

D6.6 Research design: Community and citizen responses – updated M28

Lead beneficiary: SINUS

This deliverable provides an updated research design for Work Package 6 within the COVINFORM project, offering methodological guidance and summarizing the research process to date. Work Package 6 focuses on how local contexts have influenced COVID-19 impacts and responses. The team developed five sub-questions related to spatial conditions, social networks, roles of civil society organizations (CSOs), shared attitudes, beliefs, and intra-community diversity within sub-national research sites. Interviews with representatives of CSOs in the research sites, conducted from February

to May 2022, form the basis for the findings in previous deliverables. While 38 out of 50 planned interviews were completed during this period, the remaining partners continue interviews to reach the full sample of 50 by early summer 2023. The forthcoming deliverable (D6.7) will provide a comprehensive analysis of community and citizen responses and impacts, updating the progress by month 34 of the project.

D6.7 Analysis: Community and citizen responses and impacts – update M34

Lead beneficiary: KEMEA

This report serves as an update to D6.3, focusing on community and citizen responses during the initial phases of the COVID-19 pandemic. It compiles key findings from various sources, including D6.1, D6.5, and expert interviews conducted by COVINFORM target countries until July 2023. Similar to its predecessor, D6.7 examines ten municipalities across COVINFORM countries and explores how local conditions and actors mediated the pandemic's impacts and responses. The report delves into three dimensions: local baseline conditions, changing impacts and responses throughout the pandemic, and conditions for vulnerable groups and targeted crisis management measures. The analysis emphasizes commonalities and disparities across countries during the distinct pandemic phases. The findings in D6.7 will be further detailed in D6.8, "Synthesis and lessons learnt on community and citizen responses and impacts – update," due in M36. The report concludes with lessons learned related to the three dimensions explored in this update.

D6.8 Synthesis and lessons learnt on community and citizen responses and impacts - update M36

Lead beneficiary: SINUS

D6.8 synthesizes the findings in COVINFORM work package 6, which focuses on citizen and community impacts and responses. Whereas the prior iteration (D6.4) was based on desk research and interviews with representatives of civil society organisations in ten target municipalities, this iteration also draws on the findings of interviews with low-socioeconomic-status women living in these municipalities. It addresses the research questions identified in previous deliverables (e.g., D6.6), integrating findings from both stakeholder and resident perspectives. It then derives lessons learned that are relevant to policy and practice.

WP8 outputs

2.1 White papers.

2.1.1 White paper: Participatory practices during COVID-19: Research findings and policy recommendations

Authors: Isabella Tautscher, James Edwards, Helen Rademacher & Annika Herbertz (SINUS)

Drawing on the COVINFORM project's research on civil society responses to the pandemic, this white paper offers insight into participatory practices, defined broadly as practices that, i.e., practices in which 'ordinary people' played an active and substantial role. It concludes with recommendations for policymakers on the local level on:

- 1) Supporting self-organised groups and CSOs that are motivated to help respond to a crisis;
- 2) Aligning participatory practices with governmental responses, and nudging them to fill gaps;
- 3) Leveraging participatory practices to strengthen communities.

The white paper concludes with suggested directions for future research and cooperation between researchers, policymakers, and practitioners in crisis management.

2.1.2 White paper: A social-ecological systems view on COVID-19: Research findings and policy recommendations

Authors: James Edwards (SINUS)

In an age marked by interlinked environmental and social crises of global scale, policymaking tools that account for such crises' complexity are urgently needed. The **social-ecological system framework (SESF)** offers one such tool. The concept of social-ecological systems – i.e., interlinked environmental and social systems – arose from the natural sciences, but has since found applications across the social sciences and policymaking. The COVID-19 pandemic exemplifies the complex properties of social-ecological systems, as well as the utility of the social-ecological systems framework in analysing and responding to crises. This white paper breaks down important aspects of the COVID-19 pandemic along the key domains of the social-ecological system framework:

- Governance systems
- Resource systems and units
- Actor systems
- Action situations

Drawing on data collected in ten European countries during the COVINFORM project, this white paper offers actionable recommendations for how the social-ecological systems framework can be used to add structure and focus to crisis planning and policymaking.

2.2 Bi-monthly reports

2.2.1 Bi-Monthly Report: 5 – Using an intersectional lens to understand the unequal impact of the COVID-19 pandemic

Authors: Jil Molenaar (UANTWERPEN)

This bi-monthly report draws upon insights from COVINFORM desk-based research assessing public health impact and responses to COVID-19 across COVINFORM partner countries: Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, Israel, Ireland, Italy, Germany, Greece, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom (England and Wales). The goal of this report is to outline the usefulness of an intersectional lens in considering how pre-existing structural inequalities influence COVID-19 morbidity and mortality rates, as well as in understanding how COVID-19 containment measures interact with existing structural inequalities across partner countries. The report first provides a brief introduction to intersectionality theory, highlighting its relevance for analyses of the COVID-19 pandemic. It then considers how exposure to COVID-19, as well as risk of severe disease and mortality, are shaped by pre-existing societal structures that give rise to specific inequalities. Subsequently, it presents examples of how responses to the COVID-19 crisis, such as mobility restrictions, school closures, and restrictions on events and businesses, have been experienced differently depending on people's positions in society. Throughout this report, special emphasis is placed on how people's positions at the intersections of various axes of inequality result in specific outcomes at the individual level. The report concludes by presenting some recommendations on including an intersectional lens in responding to the COVID-19 pandemic and similar crises.

2.2.2 Bi-Monthly Report: 11 – Resilience in the systems we live in: 10 European case studies

Authors: Patrick Love & Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto (FS)

This bi-monthly report presents an overview of the 10 COVINFORM's case studies which aim to identify vulnerability and protective factors of both vulnerable populations and the systems they are a part of, across different geographical settings: Portugal, Belgium, Spain, Italy, Austria, Germany, Sweden, Greece, Wales, and England. Each country selected a local site to understand how these factors enhance or mitigate COVID-19 impacts through different time points of the pandemic and contribute to provide recommendations for more effective policy making. Hence, this report presents a glimpse on how the empirical research is carried out and further information on how the case studies contribute to the 7 Objectives of the COVINFORM project and how each relates to Work Packages 4-7 may be found in Deliverables: D3.1; D3.4; and D3.5.

2.2.3 Bi-Monthly Report: 12 – A civil society organisation perspective on vulnerability: Lessons learned during COVID-19

Authors: James Edwards (SINUS)

This report focuses on lessons learned by civil society organisations (CSOs) about vulnerability during the COVID-19 pandemic: specifically, about how health, economic, social, and informational vulnerabilities emerged and evolved within EU municipalities. It is based on qualitative interviews conducted with CSO representatives who work directly with vulnerable groups, supplemented by two rounds of desk research. We asked our CSO interviewees about...

- How they understood vulnerability;
- How the pandemic impacted the vulnerable groups they work with; and
- How their organisations helped address these groups' needs.

After framing CSO interviewees' insights on certain apparent 'properties' of vulnerability, we describe specific measures that CSOs took to help address the needs of vulnerable groups. Leveraging their local knowledge and community connections often enabled CSOs to reach groups with limited access to, or trust in, governmental institutions. During the interviews, we kept an eye out for stories and situations

that the interviewees themselves found surprising, thought-provoking, inspiring, or otherwise extraordinary. Borrowing the vocabulary of institutional analysis, we call these “action situations”ⁱ. This report is based on our findings in general, but takes special account of the action situations shared by our interviewees. We present these as moments from which CSOs and other stakeholders can learn when facing future crises.

2.2.4 Bi-Monthly Report: 13 – ‘Closer to death’: thinking about dying in pandemic times

Authors: Diana Beljaars & Sergei Shubin (SU)

This bi-monthly report focuses on the changing relations people have had with death during the COVID-19 pandemic. It is based on a survey study on which the Swansea University partner collaborated with the Swansea Bay University Health Board, Neath Port Talbot Council for Voluntary Services, and Swansea Council for Voluntary Services.

2.2.5 Bi-Monthly Report: 17 – Migrant women during the pandemic_multiple and intertwined vulnerabilities

Authors: Elena Ambrosetti (SAPIENZA) & Irene Sánchez-Vitores (URJC)

This bi-monthly report is closely tied to citizen interviews conducted within COVINFORM's Work Packages 4 to 7, which analyze citizen and community responses and the impact of COVID-19. The focus of the qualitative fieldwork is specifically on understanding the gendered impacts of the pandemic by interviewing women with low socioeconomic status (SES). This group was selected for meaningful cross-country comparisons as low SES consistently emerged as a risk factor across different countries. The fieldwork, guided by COVINFORM's intersectional theoretical framework, employs social network analysis to examine relationship patterns and resource exchange among individuals and organizations. Social networks play a vital role in determining access to influence and power, impacting diverse experiences during the pandemic. The report emphasizes that the analysis of interview transcripts contributes to a better understanding of how people mitigate disadvantages and highlights the non-homogeneity of groups with shared characteristics, such as gender and socioeconomic status. Each project partner engaged with Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) to conduct a minimum of 12 interviews per research site, using a semi-structured interview framework developed by COVINFORM researchers. The interviews explore experiences from the start of the pandemic to July 2022, providing flexibility for unfolding conversations in seven main topic areas.

2.3 Blog posts

2.3.1 Emergency medical service responders reflect on the pandemic: Interventions in Israel and Spain – Part I

Authors: James Edwards (SINUS)

Published on October 20, 2023, the blog post serves as the first part of a series that delves into the experiences and reflections of emergency medical service (EMS) responders in Israel and Spain amid the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. Part I focuses on the participatory interventions conducted by COVINFORM partners Magen David Adom (MDA) in Israel and S.A.M.U.R. Protección Civil (SAMUR) in Madrid. The blog provides a comprehensive exploration of the workshops organized with EMS professionals, both volunteers and paid staff, aiming to validate COVINFORM research

findings and involve responders in the project. It sheds light on their perspectives regarding vaccination campaigns, risk communication, and the unique stresses experienced during the pandemic. The insights shared by EMS responders highlight critical areas for improvement in resource management, mental health support, and communication strategies, setting the stage for further discussions on enhancing pandemic response effectiveness and support for frontline healthcare workers.

2.3.2 Emergency medical service responders reflect on the pandemic: Interventions in Israel and Spain – Part II

Authors: James Edwards (SINUS)

Published on October 24, 2023, the blog post is the second part of a series examining the reflections of emergency medical service (EMS) responders in Israel and Spain on pandemic interventions. Part II explores the insights gained from workshops conducted in Tel Aviv and Madrid, focusing on the experiences of EMS responders during the COVID-19 pandemic. The blog delves into the challenges faced by responders, such as increased workloads, resource management issues, and the psychological impact of their roles. It underscores the importance of effective health and risk communication planning, emphasizing the need for audience testing and better attention to vulnerable groups. Additionally, the blog highlights the underappreciated role of EMS responders as a valuable source of lived wisdom and data during health crises, shedding light on the gaps in public health policies and systems. The insights gathered contribute to a deeper understanding of the experiences and perspectives of EMS professionals, providing valuable guidance for future public health crises.

2.3.3 Understanding the Systems we Live in: Deconstructing the Systems we Live by

Authors: Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto (FS)

The blog post, dated September 28, 2023, delves into the concept of syndemics, a term coined by medical anthropologist Merrill Singer in the 90s, emphasizing the overlap of epidemics with social and cultural problems, making the impact more hindering than the sum of its parts. It explores how the syndemic approach is crucial in understanding the interplay of diseases, social determinants, and systemic factors during the COVID-19 pandemic. The post argues for the importance of addressing political-economic forces, historical inequities, and the overlapping effects of diseases to comprehensively combat health crises. It also critiques the syndemic approach for not adequately addressing deeper political and economic factors and highlights the importance of an intersectional analysis. The COVINFORM project, incorporating an Intersectional approach and Socio-ecological Systems Framework, aims to understand the socio-economic impacts of COVID-19 and the dynamics between various systems within society. The post concludes by emphasizing the need to enhance system resilience, as demonstrated by the SES framework, to effectively respond to future pandemics.

2.3.4 How COVID-19 has exposed housing inequalities: insights from Antwerp

Authors: Hanna Robinson (UANTWERPEN)

The blog post, published on June 21, 2023, explores how the COVID-19 pandemic has exposed housing inequalities in Antwerp, Belgium. Interviews with migrants reveal that access to green spaces and gardens during the pandemic provided comfort, contrasting with the disadvantages faced by those in crowded apartments without space for children to play. Rising rent and cost-of-living issues, exacerbated by the pandemic's economic consequences, have further disadvantaged lower-income residents. The financialization of housing in Antwerp, with smaller dwellings at higher prices,

contributes to a shrinking market segment for lower-income residents. Coping mechanisms include informal housing practices and community networks. The post emphasizes the need to invest in organizations supporting marginalized groups, diversify housing types, implement tenant protection policies, and prioritize the needs of marginalized groups in urban planning to prevent displacement and ensure well-being during crises.

2.3.5 Where did the UK go wrong in preparing for the COVID-19 pandemic, and how have preparedness failings tainted public trust among the UK population?

Authors: Zainab Mehdi (TRI)

The blog post, dated December 15, 2022, critically examines the UK's response to the COVID-19 pandemic, identifying key failings that impacted public trust. The first major criticism is the adoption of the 'Herd Immunity' approach, where the government, under Boris Johnson's administration, initially favored managing the virus rather than implementing prompt lockdowns. This strategy resulted in rapid virus spread, thousands of deaths among the elderly, and strain on the National Health Service (NHS). The second criticism revolves around the inadequate implementation of pandemic exercises and the failure to learn from Exercise Cygnus, a relevant trial conducted in 2016. Another significant blow to public trust was the revelation of government officials breaking lockdown rules, known as "Partygate," leading to an internal inquiry and police fines. The findings of these events have eroded public trust in the government's pandemic handling. The post emphasizes the need for transparency, investment in anthropological research, and meaningful engagement with the public to rebuild trust, especially in anticipation of future pandemics.

2.3.6 Compulsory vaccinations and skipping contact restrictions – differing narratives of freedom in the German middle class

Authors: James Edwards & Tim Gensheimer (SINUS)

The blog post, dated July 12, 2022, explores German middle-class perspectives on COVID-19 vaccinations and compulsory vaccination. A nationally representative survey conducted by SINUS-Institut in spring 2022 reveals that while Germans value personal autonomy in vaccination decisions, with 63% opposing compulsory vaccinations, 85% believe individuals shouldn't be attacked based on their vaccination status. The Sinus-Milieu model identifies distinct social segments interpreting freedom differently, impacting their reactions to external restrictions. For instance, the Performers and Consumer-Hedonistic Milieus lean towards hedonism and self-determination, reacting negatively to restrictions, while the Adaptive-Pragmatic and Nostalgic Middle Class Milieus expect crisis policies to balance health and private sphere sanctity. The polarizing COVID policies have affected personal relationships, with 20% losing friends due to differing opinions. The COVINFORM project further investigates these dynamics to provide insights for policymakers aiming to enhance compliance while respecting individual autonomy.

2.3.7 “Un-masking the Mask-Issue”: Examining People’s Sense-Making Processes and Risk-Cultural Norms regarding Facemasks

Authors: Tim Arasimowicz (UGOT)

The blog post, dated April 24, 2022, delves into the cultural norms and values influencing people's perceptions of facemasks in Sweden during the COVID-19 pandemic. It emphasizes the role of risk-cultural classifications, categorizing individuals based on their beliefs about foreseeing crises,

responsibilities, and trust in authorities and media. The study, conducted through qualitative focus groups, explores how individuals with different backgrounds interpreted information and formed attitudes toward facemasks. Findings reveal distinct patterns among groups with Swedish and foreign backgrounds, highlighting initial reactions, media trust, and risk-cultural norms. While the Swedish group perceived mask-wearing as a private matter, those with foreign backgrounds expected authorities to regulate it. The study underscores the importance of nuanced communication strategies in a multi-public society, considering diverse perceptions and behaviors in crisis information interpretation.

2.3.8 Antisemitic narratives find ground in COVID-19 anti-vax conspiracy theories

Authors: *Marianna Karakoulaki (MDI)*

The blog post, dated December 12, 2021, delves into the intersection of antisemitic narratives and COVID-19 anti-vax conspiracy theories, drawing attention to the prominent role of social media in spreading such ideologies. Examining Facebook and Twitter posts from March to August 2021, the report, part of the Get The Trolls Out! project, notes how anti-vaxxers use Holocaust comparisons, consider themselves the 'new Jews,' and employ coded language like 'globalists' to convey antisemitic sentiments. The study identifies variations of established antisemitic conspiracy ideologies, fearmongering, victim mentality, and connections to the far right as significant factors. The report urges improved social media moderation, consistent enforcement of hate speech policies, deplatforming of conspiracists, and collaboration among tech companies to address the alarming spread of antisemitic content within anti-vax conspiracy theories on social media.

2.3.9 Pandemic mitigation for everyone: Ethnic differences in Wales

Authors: *Diana Beljaars, Sergei Shubin & Louise Condon (SU)*

The blog post, dated November 23, 2021, discusses ethnic differences in perceptions and responses to the COVID-19 pandemic and mitigation measures in Wales. Based on a survey conducted in the Swansea and Neath Port Talbot area, the study focuses on the experiences of Black Asian and minority ethnic (BAME) individuals compared to white individuals. The survey reveals variations in estimations of vulnerability, testing behavior, and vaccine uptake between ethnic groups. Notably, BAME respondents showed lower intention and acceptance of COVID-19 vaccination, citing concerns about vaccine development, effectiveness, and a need for more information. The authors stress the importance of considering ethnic differences in pandemic responses, suggesting that policies and communications should be sensitive to the racial contexts and historical concerns of diverse populations to address disproportionate suffering along ethnic lines.

2.3.10 Why gender matters in the COVID-19 response

Authors: *Su Anson (TRI), Viktoria Adler (SYNYO), Diotima Bertel (SYNYO) & Maureen Fordham*

The blog post, dated August 3, 2021, underscores the gendered impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic, emphasizing the importance of considering gender differences in disaster planning and policy. Gender, defined as a socially constructed concept distinct from biological sex, is approached through an intersectional lens, recognizing the interconnectedness of various social categories. The COVINFORM project focuses on analyzing the pandemic's impact on different social groups, with gender as a key category of analysis. Research on gender and disasters reveals that disasters, including the ongoing pandemic, disproportionately affect individuals based on gender, influencing risk perception,

preparedness, response, and recovery. The blog outlines specific gender-based impacts of COVID-19, such as employment exposure, economic disparities, and an increase in domestic violence. It calls for policies that go beyond oversimplified labels, considering diverse impacts and vulnerabilities based on characteristics and identity categories. The COVINFORM project aims to examine and address these gender-specific impacts and vulnerabilities within the context of pandemic responses.

2.4 Podcasts and videos

2.4.1 Podcast: 5 – Community voices - Bringing it all together

Participants: Eliza Jordan (TRI), James Edwards (SINUS), Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto (FS)

How were different communities impacted by the COVID19 pandemic? On the fifth podcast episode we will listen to a series of stories from civil society organisations shedding light on the experiences of vulnerable groups during the pandemic. The experts on today's episode, James Edwards and Madalena Ricoca-Peixoto, will draw conclusions from the stories and showcase lessons learnt from the COVID19 pandemic. Link: <https://rss.com/podcasts/beyondnumbers/844007/>

2.4.2 Video: Elements of community -- Introduction

Participants: James Edwards (SINUS)

COVINFORM is a research project, which aims to analyse the effect of Covid-19 impact responses and identify strategies for inclusive and effective pandemic communication. The project is funded by the EU Horizon2020 program. During the project, we talked to 50 civil society organisations in 10 countries about how they informed and supported their communities during the pandemic and found that their ability to act on a community level often proved critical. What is a community? In the broadest sense, “communities” are groups of people that have something in common. In our research, we found that the five “elements of community”, as defined by MacQueen et al. (2001) were particularly important:

- Shared locations
- Shared characteristics and behaviours
- Shared relationships and social ties
- Shared activities
- Shared respect for diversity within the community

In our video series, we share the stories of how three civil society organisations leveraged these five elements to support their communities during the pandemic. Link: <https://youtu.be/w9WcHCiozpl?feature=shared>

2.4.1 Video: Elements of community – Shared locations

Participants: Ilka Sobotka (external stakeholder)

In our research, we found that a civil society organisation’s ability to leverage the five elements of community (MacQueen et al., 2001) was often critical in their efforts to support and inform vulnerable groups during Covid-19. One element of community is SHARED LOCATION, research shows. During the Covid-19 pandemic, shared location was especially hard to realize. Mannheim pastor Ilka Sobotke explains how she insisted on keeping the church doors open during the pandemic to provide her community with a contact point, which was especially important for people without internet access. Link: <https://youtu.be/jMizmrOOF2w?feature=shared>

2.4.1 Video: Elements of community -- Diversity

Participants: Ilka Sobotka (external stakeholder)

Another element of community is DIVERSITY. Mannheim pastor Ilka Sobottke recounts how she created the “generation breakfast”, an initiative to bring together the older people in her community with the young refugees living in the neighbourhood. By creating a safe space to meet and interact, she was able to strengthen the understanding between the two groups, and their respect for each other’s differences. Link: <https://youtu.be/Pypx95ZE7Ow?feature=shared>

2.4.1 Video: Elements of community – Joint action

Participants: Markus Priller (AUTRC)

Another element of community is TAKING JOINT ACTION. Markus Priller at the Austrian Red Cross explains how people worked together during the pandemic to establish security and to inform their own communities about Covid-19 and the restrictions. Link: <https://youtu.be/KP4-vZQKHQg?feature=shared>

2.4.1 Video: Elements of community – Shared characteristics and behaviours

Participants: Dr. Suad Mohamed (AUTRC)

Another element of community is SHARED CHARACTERISTICS AND BEHAVIOURS. Dr. Suad Mohamed explains how she launched an initiative together with the Austrian Red Cross to inform the Somali community in Austria about Covid-19 and the restrictions during the pandemic. She understood the importance of a common language and cultural background when communicating such critical information, which is why she gave the floor to Somali doctors. Link: <https://youtu.be/z98TjJHbeHk?feature=shared>

2.4.1 Video: Elements of community – Social ties

Participants: Chaim Rafalowski (MDA)

A final element of community is SOCIAL TIES. Chaim Rafalowski at Magen David Adom in Israel explains how they initiated “family talks”, where Magen David Adom volunteers would inform their families about the Covid-19 vaccines, as they understood that healthcare workers turned into a trusted source of information for their personal network. Link: <https://youtu.be/BkdbDbR9Fjw?feature=shared>

2.5 Scientific publications

Migrants as ‘vulnerable groups’ in the COVID-19 pandemic: A critical discourse analysis of a taken-for-granted label in academic literature.

Authors: Jil Molenaar & Lore Van Praag (UANTWERPEN). Citation: Molenaar, J., & Van Praag, L. (2022). Migrants as ‘vulnerable groups’ in the COVID-19 pandemic: A critical discourse analysis of a taken-for-granted label in academic literature. *SSM-Qualitative Research in Health*, 2, 100076. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmqr.2022.100076>

Using critical discourse analysis methods, this article analyses the academic use of the term ‘vulnerable’ applied to migrants in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic across public health and social science disciplines. The findings indicate that the concept of vulnerability is frequently applied to migrants in the COVID-19 context as a descriptor with seemingly taken-for-granted applicability. Additionally, the analysis revealed widespread generalization in the use of the notion of vulnerability,

with limited consideration of the heterogeneity among and between diverse groups of migrants. Conceptualizations of migrants' vulnerability in the COVID-19 pandemic were sometimes used to advance seemingly contradictory policy implications or conclusions, and migrants' own views and lived experiences were often marginalized or excluded within these discourses. The analysis highlights that although some definable groups of people are certainly more likely to suffer harm in crisis situations like the COVID-19 pandemic, the use of 'vulnerable' as a fixed descriptor has potentially negative implications. As an alternative, the authors suggest thinking about vulnerability as the dynamic outcome of a process of 'vulnerabilisation' shaped by social order and power relations.

Reproductions of vulnerability: The inequitable realities of the Welsh policy and pandemic response procedures

Authors: *Diana Beljaars, Sergei Shubin, & Louise Condon (SU)*. Conference paper during the American Association of Geographers Annual Conference 2022 (online). In session: "Interlocking Oppressions and COVID-19". The text is not made readily available, but it can be provided on request.

This conference paper reports on how COVID-19 and the governmental responses to the pandemic in Wales affect the experiences of groups that faced relatively high levels of suffering, illness, and death. It focuses on people whose lives unfold according to alternative mobilities, such as migrants and Gypsy, Romani, and Travellers. It reveals how precarious pandemic circumstances were compounded by intersecting processes of oppression, including through race and gender. These reflections provide new insights into how vulnerability is understood, negated, and reproduced in neoliberal state and local policy as well as in the organisation of healthcare in Wales.

Constructing viral subjectivities during the pandemic: women's embodiment in Wales

Authors: *Diana Beljaars & Sergei Shubin (SU)*. Conference paper during the American Association of Geographers Annual Conference 2023 (Denver, CO). In session: "Bodies, Health, and Space". The text is not made readily available, but it can be provided on request. It is currently near submission to academic journal *GeoForum*.

To better understand the unequal impact of pandemic regulations for different social groups, this paper looks at how body-virus relations have underpinned the pandemic realities. It does so by focussing on the subject formation constructed following life scientific knowledge creation versus the lived pandemic subjectivities of minority ethnic women with a low socio-economic status in South Wales. Its findings include the inadequate ontologisation of body-virus relations as materially separate, inaccurate anticipation of rationality, and an insufficient understanding of uncertainty. Compounding exclusionary mechanisms became visible in the experiences of 18 refugees, asylum seekers, unemployed women, and healthcare workers.

In review: A Beacon of Hope: A Qualitative Study on Migrants' Mental Health Needs and Community-Based Organizations' Responses During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Antwerp, Belgium

Authors: *Hannah Robinson, Jil Molenaar, Lore van Praag (UANTWERPEN)*

Provides an assessment of how community organisations have responded to mental health needs during the pandemic.

In review: Feeling Stuck: The Micro-Politics of Migrant Dwelling Practices During COVID-19 in Antwerp

Authors: *Hannah Robinson, Jil Molenaar, Lore van Praag (UANTWERPEN)*

Explores how migrant micro-politics took place within a context of spatial inequalities during the pandemic.

3 Conclusion

This deliverable summarised outputs produced in WP6 on community and citizen responses and impacts, as well as transversal outputs relevant to its focal topics.

Policy recommendations based on the WP6 findings can be summarised as follows:

Recommendation 1: Establish infrastructures that expedite participatory crisis responses

Broaden digital infrastructures

The success of COVID-19 initiatives heavily relied on digital access, as demonstrated by online campaigns and social media utilization. To enhance digital access, key strategies involve ensuring affordable broadband internet in rural areas, providing hardware to access the internet, and supporting the acquisition of skills to navigate the internet.

Deepen fiscal infrastructures

Access to financial resources, whether from government funding or networking initiatives, significantly enhances the impact of participatory practices. Local governments can further support such efforts by providing matching grants, creating extraordinary funding frameworks with reduced bureaucratic barriers and implementing participatory budgeting processes.

Streamline institutional infrastructures

Despite local governments' efforts to collaborate with CSOs during the pandemic, institutional structures and bureaucratic procedures became crippling. Suggested measures for improving crisis-readiness include establishing a single contact point for CSOs, waiving bureaucratic hurdles for projects addressing critical needs, fostering a culture of participation and trust during non-crisis periods, and creating an environment where opposing viewpoints are respected.

Recommendation 2: Empower a spectrum of practices, from those directly sponsored by government to those that are fully autonomous

Directly sponsor diverse initiatives under umbrella programmes

Participatory practices co-sponsored by the government provide a suitable platform for smaller, temporary projects addressing areas outside core social welfare systems. Microgrant schemes offer an effective means to support diverse yet coordinated projects, including food banks, medication delivery services, defibrillator initiatives, support services for migrants and international students, and digital capacity building for organizations like the National Autistic Society.

Improve coordination with independent CSO-led initiatives

During the initial phase of the pandemic, participatory practices, initiated independently by self-organized groups or civil society organizations, served as rapid and agile stopgap measures to supplement overstressed public sector services, addressing both basic needs and more complex aims, highlighting the potential for governments to delegate responsibilities to civil society during crises and

emphasizing the importance of proactive collaboration between governmental organizations and CSOs to avoid gaps in responses and leverage the capacities of these initiatives effectively.

Allow space for intentionally autonomous practices

A minority of identified practices intentionally operated independently from government organizations, such as autonomous initiatives could serve as alternative pathways of support for population groups with low trust in government, and governments could learn from them to better prepare for future crises by reviewing actors and strategies, identifying response gaps, and ensuring limits on non-interference are in place

Use participatory practices to leverage existing networks

Participatory practices during crises, involving ordinary residents, organizers, volunteers, and civil society, often centred around shared communities with common interests and relied on shared social networks, underscoring the importance of trust and community bonds for effective crisis responses. Fostering such practices can provide crisis responders access to community networks, especially in areas with low trust in government, where civil society or self-organized groups may be more effective initiators.

Recommendation 3: Incorporate the social-ecological systems framework as a tool in crisis planning and crisis-aware policymaking

Get proactive about multi-level governance

The ad-hoc nature of the involvement of CSOs and challenges in coordination with government planners highlight the need for proactive measures, such as inclusive planning involving CSOs in the early development of response strategies, policies, and procedures and establishing bi-directional feedback channels for real-time improvement of response strategies and advocacy for structural inequality alleviation.

Treat social networks and capital as ‘system-critical’ resources

Especially for residents with limited exposure to formal welfare systems social networks play a vital role in pandemic response, highlighting the importance of considering investments in social and community capital as integral to crisis planning and preparation. Governments can achieve this by promoting social interactions, enhancing infrastructure, organizing networking opportunities, building capacities, and providing funding and recognition for CSOs and self-organized groups. The impact of disruptions to social networks during lockdowns must be carefully considered to avoid leaving vulnerable individuals without both formal and informal support systems.

Go beyond buzzwords on diversity and inclusion

Intra-community differences were exacerbated by the pandemic, highlighting the need for investments in combating inequality and discrimination as part of crisis preparation. Local governments are urged to commit to inclusivity, review and reinforce anti-discrimination laws, establish reporting mechanisms, enhance cultural competency training, and promote diverse representation. CSOs and residents can play a crucial role in leveraging trust and social networks for accurate information dissemination and health-protective behaviour encouragement among marginalized groups during crises.